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Bending Behaviour of Medium Manganese Steels in Relation to Thermomechanical Processing Parameters

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Abstract

The bending behaviour of a medium manganese steel containing 5 wt. % Mn was examined within EU WarP-AHSS project, which aims at developing tailored steels for automotive industry. After cold rolling to 1.5 mm gauge, the steel underwent a double intercritical annealing treatment: i) a first annealing at 700 °C, 730 °C, or 760 °C (simulating continuous annealing with galvanizing); and (ii) a second annealing at either 700 °C or 750 °C to simulate hot press forming. Bending tests were performed according to VDA238-100 standard. Bending tests aimed at investigating the effects of the heat treatment parameters and bending axis orientation on the deformability of the developed material, expressed by bending angle at the occurrence of cracks. Due to the directionality of the microstructure along the rolling direction, the bending angles were in general lower, in all conditions, when the bending axis is transverse the rolling direction. After single annealing at 700 °C, the steel demonstrated the highest ductility with achieved bending angles in the range of 61-97 °, because of a duplex microstructure of ferrite with high fraction of retained austenite (22 vol.% with carbon content $C_\gamma = 0.38$ wt.%), giving a more efficient transformation induced plasticity (TRIP) effect. When the annealing temperature increased to 730 °C and 760 °C, the achieved bending angles decreased to 33-47° and cracks became apparent. This is because part of the reverted austenite partially transformed into hard martensite during room temperature cooling, leading to a final mixture of ferrite, martensite and austenite (23 vol.% and 10 vol.% with C_γ of 0.29 and 0.2 wt.%, both respectively) in the microstructure. After hot press forming at 700 °C, irrespective of the first annealing temperature, the bending angle was in the range of 55-79°. The microstructural constituents, after the second annealing or hot press forming at 700 °C, were again ferrite and retained austenite, with increased carbon content compared to the first annealing due to further carbon and manganese partitioning during austenite reversion, causing more efficient TRIP effect. However, after second annealing at 750 °C, the achieved bending angles were markedly reduced, in some cases below 40°, due to a reduced austenite stability leading to the formation of fresh martensite.

1 Introduction

Within the EU-Project, “Warm Press-Formed Zinc-Coated Third Generation Advanced High Strength Steels with High Crash and Corrosion Resistance and Minimized Microcracking” (WarP-AHSS) new medium manganese steels (MMnS) are being developed [1, 2, 3]. These steels aim at achieving tensile strength (R_m) above 1500 MPa with a total elongation (A_{50}) of $\geq 10\%$ to realize anti-intrusion components, and $R_m \geq 1200$ MPa with A_{50} above 18% after hot forming in case of high-energy absorbing parts. The typical material currently used in this scenario is boron-added hot press forming (HPF) steels, such as 22MnB5 (yield strength $R_{p0.2} \approx 1000$ MPa, $R_m \approx 1500$ MPa and $A_{50} \approx 6\%$). Hot forming process has advantages, including high formability and low springback, compared to cold forming processes [4], however the conventional process is characterized by several disadvantages, such as: i) high-energy cost caused by high austenitizing/reheating temperatures, ii) low durability of press dies due to thermal fatigue, and iii) low productivity due to the relatively long die quenching time of 5–10 s demanded by the critical cooling rate of boron-added steels.

Recently, due to their superior attainable mechanical properties, deriving from a duplex/triplex microstructure consisting of ferrite, reverted austenite and martensite and the transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP), MMnS (3–12 wt.% Mn) emerged as candidates for the new generation of car body parts. In fact, due to the high manganese content, the critical transformation temperatures (austenite start and finish temperatures, A_{c1} and A_{c3} respectively) are significantly reduced, leading to a warm forming process [5]. Furthermore, due to the fact that the reheating temperature will be significantly lower compared to that of the 22MnB5, MMnS can also be used in Zn-coated condition in hot forming. Considering that car structural components deform and fracture under stress conditions close to plane-strain bending during vehicle crashes [6], plane-strain bendability, according to VDA238-100 standard [7, 8] represents a key material property for hot-formed steels. Recent research has revealed that both the volume fraction and the mechanical stability of retained austenite (RA) significantly affect the three-point bending behaviour [6]. In particular, it has been observed that, in martensitic/austenitic microstructure, martensitic transformation of unstable retained austenite leads to crack nucleation at the austenite/martensite interface. However, the number of studies on the bendability on MMnS is still limited. The present study, therefore, examines the effects of single (continuous annealing-only) and double (continuous annealing + intercritical reheating for HPF simulation) annealing routes on the plane-strain bending response of MMnS.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Alloy and processing

In this paper the results from one MMnS are reported. The steel is a low-carbon 5 wt.% Mn-containing MMnS, denoted as Alloy A. The alloy was cast in pilot-scale (80 kg ingot) and processed to 1.5 mm final gauge by cold rolling following hot rolling, the austenite start (A_{c1}), austenite finish (A_{c3}) and martensite start (M_s) temperatures of the MMnS as determined by high-resolution dilatometry were 690, 825 and 322 °C respectively.

2.2 Heat treatments

After the cold rolling, a first annealing step (continuous annealing), combined with galvanizing simulation (470 °C, 72 s), was applied with peak annealing temperatures of 700 °C, 730 °C and 760 °C (soaking time of 62 s). After the annealing treatments, thermal simulations for HPF cycles were conducted to investigate the effects of blank reheating temperature on the HPF cycles. Two reheating temperatures ($T_{\text{HPF}} = 700 \text{ °C}$ and 750 °C) were selected. These temperatures lie in the intercritical temperature range (A_{c1} to A_{c3}) of the alloy and are much lower than the reheating temperatures used for conventional boron steel (870 - 940 °C). The chosen reheating temperatures were based on Tata Steel's prior experience with medium manganese steels: in particular 700 °C was chosen since it is generally safe for the liquid metal embrittlement during hot forming with a zinc coating, while 750 °C was also included because one of the target tensile strength levels in this project is $\geq 1500 \text{ MPa}$ which is expected to require a reheating temperature high in the intercritical temperature range to achieve martensite in the final microstructure. **Table 1** summarizes the performed heat treatments. All the annealing treatments were performed in a Rhesca simulator at Tata Steel with sheet dimensions of 200 mm x 120 mm x 1.5 mm, and subsequently the HPF cycles were performed at Volkswagen.

Table 1: Summary of the heat treatments carried out on the investigated alloy

Alloy	Continuous annealing (CA) temperature [°C]	Hot press forming (HPF) temperature [°C]
A	700, 730, 760	700, 750

2.3 Bending test methodology

VDA238-100 standard specifies a small-plate, three-point bending method to determine the bending angle of metallic sheet materials under tight-radius conditions. The metric supports material ranking for bending-dominated forming (e.g., hemming) and crash-relevant load cases in automotive applications. The details of the bending test methodology according to the specification are described below.

Specimens. Flat samples (30 mm× 60 mm) are cut from the sheet material. Surfaces must be clean and edges finished (e.g., deburred/ground) to avoid edge-initiated artifacts. Where very large bend angles are expected (ductile or thin-gauge sheets), the guideline allows pre-straining in uniaxial tension to prevent inconclusive fold-over without fracture; such pre-straining were not used in our investigations.

Fixture. A three-point rig with two lower support rollers and a sharp upper punch is used. Punch tip radius is 0.4 mm, representative of hemming and crash folding. The roller span is set as a function of sheet thickness t and the target angle α ; common practice is $\approx 2 \cdot t + 0.5 \text{ mm}$. To ensure measured angles reflect material behaviour rather than rig compliance, the fixture must pass a stiffness verification (total widening of the rollers $\leq 0.1 \text{ mm}$ at 3000 N).

Procedure & stop conditions. The specimen is centrally loaded until a defined failure threshold is reached. VDA238-100 standard uses a load-drop criterion to indicate crack initiation/propagation: a 30 N (for $t < 2$ mm) decreases in force after the maximum force. The standard also permits alternative stop conditions—e.g., a crosshead-travel limit (to reach the expected angle without fixture interference) or a significant force rise—to avoid tool-contact artifacts at very high angles.

Angle determination. Three methods are used: (i) manual protractor measurement post-test (plastically deformed specimens only), (ii) calculation from crosshead travel (elastic + plastic), and (iii) optical, camera-based measurement during loading (elastic + plastic) [9]. Please note that the load drop threshold is a practical proxy for crack initiation in higher-strength grades, but can yield false positives (apparent “failure”) in ductile or thin-gauge steels that fold over without cracking [7]. Bending tests of sheet steels are thus widely used to quantify local formability.

2.4 Bending experiments

Three-point bending tests, on 1.5 mm-thick samples of Alloy A after the various heat treatments, were carried out as per VDA238-100 standard described above. Bending samples of dimensions 30 mm × 60 mm were extracted from the heat-treated sheets from both longitudinal (BA-L) and transverse (BA-T) directions. The samples were cleaned by citric acid to remove the oxides from the surface. It was ensured that the bending axis resides in the homogeneous temperature area of the heat-treated sheets. Tests were carried out in both longitudinal and transverse specimens with a punch radius of 0.4 mm. Bending samples were taken out from 2 to 4 Rhesca treated sheets for each condition (2–4 samples from each direction per sheet), giving statistically meaningful data. The bending angle is calculated according to the equation in the VDA238-100 standard. The average values of the bending angles are reported for each condition.

2.5 Microstructure characterization and tensile tests

Observation of the microstructural constituents was performed on the plane of rolling direction and normal direction (RD–ND) by a field emission gun scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM), while the phases, e.g. retained austenite (V_γ in vol. %) and ferrite/martensite at room temperature were identified and quantified by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Austenite carbon content (C_γ in wt.%) was estimated from refined lattice parameters using an empirical correlation [1]. The measurement errors of V_γ and C_γ are ± 3 vol.% and ± 0.02 wt.% respectively. Vickers microhardness (HV1) was measured at mid-thickness using a 1 kgf load, averaging the values from at least five indentations. Mini-tensile specimens with 2.5 mm gauge length and 2 mm gauge width were machined in the rolling direction by electro-discharge machining (EDM) from samples heat treated in a dilatometer and tested with a quasi-static strain rate. The total elongation values were converted to values conforming to Euronorm A₅₀ specimen geometry using Oliver’s formula [10] and both total elongation values ($A_{2.5}$ and A_{50}) are reported.

3 Results

3.1 Microstructure and tensile properties

After reheating at 700 °C for HPF, the microstructure of Alloy A results in a mixture of ferrite and austenite, while after treatment at 750 °C, martensite was also detected in the microstructure. As the temperature increases, the amount of formed reverted austenite increases (Table 2). However, a higher temperature HPF results in reverted austenite with less enrichment of carbon and manganese and therefore its thermal stability decreases, leading to martensitic transformation upon room temperature cooling. This agrees with the reduced volume fraction and carbon content of retained austenite measured by XRD after HPF treatment at 750 °C. The retained austenite contents and the carbon enrichment values of the samples after first annealing are given in Table 3. The volume fraction of retained austenite decreases as the annealing temperature increases from 700 to 760 °C due to lower enrichment of carbon (an also possibly Mn also) in the intercritical austenite during annealing. This would mean also the martensite fraction in the microstructure would increase with the annealing temperature at the expense of retained austenite.

The tensile properties of the investigated Alloy A are also summarized in Table . An increase in yield strength ($R_{p0.2}$), tensile strength (R_m) and HV1 is observed when the HPF simulation temperature rises (from 700 to 750 °C), while the uniform elongation (A_g) and total elongation (A_{50}) decreases. This behaviour is attributed to the formation of fresh martensite during cooling when the material is treated at 750 °C and the consequent reduction in the austenite volume fraction. This interpretation is consistent with the evolution of retained austenite reported in Table 2: on one hand the brittle behaviour of martensite contributes to improve the strength, and on the other hand the reduced carbon content reduces the mechanical stability of austenite making the TRIP effect less effective in delaying the insurgence of instability and fracture.

Table 2: Tensile properties, retained austenite volume fractions (V_γ) and carbon contents (C_γ) in the retained austenite for Alloy A. The measurement errors of V_γ and C_γ are ± 3 vol.% and ± 0.02 wt.% respectively.

Annealing Temp. [°C]	HPF Temp. [°C]	$R_{p0.2}$ [MPa]	R_m [MPa]	A_g [%]	$A_{2.5}$ [%]	A_{50} [%]	HV1	V_γ [vol.%]	C_γ [wt.%]
700	700	649	1214	18.2	41.8	14.8	356	29	0.37
	750	780	1657	7.1	7.5	5.1	519	12	0.20
730	700	647	1265	19.5	37.6	9.9	417	32	0.34
	750	911	1617	12.1	13.3	4.2	468	13	0.20
760	700	474	1343	17.6	36.6	18.9	374	37	0.37
	750	765	1672	12.5	19.6	7.3	470	17	0.23

3.2 Bendability

The results of the bending tests carried out according to VDA238-100 standard are given in Table 3 and Table 4 after first annealing and after HPF. The bending angles of the longitudinal samples (BA-L) are in general higher than the bending angles of the transverse (BA-T) samples for all the conditions. This is due to the alignment of grains along the rolling direction with the bending axis perpendicular to it reducing bending related ductility in the transverse samples. After the first annealing,

the bending angle in both directions decreases with increasing annealing temperature (Table 3), most probably due to reduced amount and stability of retained austenite (as indicated by lower carbon content).

A systematic variation in the bending response of Alloy A as a function of HPF temperature is also observed. For a given first annealing temperature, the bending angle decreases with increase in the HPF temperature (Table 4) due to the decrease in retained austenite fraction and its carbon content (Table 2) and concomitant formation of fresh martensite. This can be also correlated with the tensile response given in **Table 2**, where increase in strength and decrease in total elongation can be observed with increasing HPF temperature. For HPF at 700 °C, the BA-L ranges between ~69° to 79°, whereas the BA-T value is in the range of ~54–61° irrespective of the first annealing temperature. For the first annealing at 700 °C and 730 °C, the BA-L values with 750 °C HPF are ~55° and the BA-T values are in a narrow range of ~38–42°. However, for first annealing at 760 °C, increasing the HPF temperature to 750 °C markedly reduces BA-L value (to as low as 35.3°), and the BA-T value was close to zero degree because the material fractured very soon after the bending test started. This brittle behaviour is consistent with the concurrent strength increase and ductility loss due to the formation of fresh martensite.

Table 3: Bending angles and the retained austenite volume fraction (V_γ) and its carbon content (C_γ) for Alloy A after the first annealing step. The measurement errors of V_γ and C_γ are ± 3 vol.% and ± 0.02 wt.% respectively.

Annealing Temperature [°C]	BA-L [°]	BA-T [°]	V_γ [vol.%]	C_γ [wt.%]
700	97.0	60.5	22	0.38
730	46.7	36.5	23	0.29
760	44.8	33.4	10	0.20

Table 4: Results of the bending tests in longitudinal and transversal direction carried out on Alloy A according to VDA238-100 standard.

Annealing Temperature [°C]	HPF Temperature [°C]	BA-L [°]	BA-T [°]
700	700	79.2	58.7
	750	54.7	37.6
730	700	68.9	53.9
	750	54.5	42.1
760	700	76.2	61.1
	750	35.3	crack

In order to visualize the microstructure dependence, the bending angle of the longitudinal samples (BA-L) as a function of retained austenite content has been plotted in **Figure 1**. For HPF = 750 °C, all specimens exhibit $V_\gamma \approx 10$ –17 %, whereas for HPF = 700 °C, the retained austenite contents are higher (≈ 29 –37 %). Consequently, higher V_γ is generally associated with higher BA-L: the HPF = 700 °C conditions cluster around ~70–80°, while the HPF = 750 °C conditions lie around

~35–55°. The trend is not strictly monotonic, reflecting the additional roles of austenite stability ($C\gamma$), martensite fraction/distribution, and texture on bendability.

Figure 1: Bending angle of the longitudinal samples (BA-L) vs. retained austenite for Alloy A under different combinations of annealing temperature (Ann. T) and hot press forming temperature (HPF).

4 Conclusion

From this current work, it can be concluded that with increasing annealing and HPF temperature a 5 wt.% Mn-containing low-carbon medium manganese steel achieves higher tensile strength with lower tensile elongation. This is due to presence of lesser amounts of retained austenite with lower stability and freshly formed martensite. The bendability of the steel, measured according to VDA238-100 standard, also generally shows an inverse relation with the tensile strength due to these microstructural characteristics. Bendability of longitudinal samples exhibits higher values than the transverse samples. The HPF at 700 °C, irrespective of the annealing temperature in the range of 700-760 °C, gives reasonably high bendability, which decreases when the steel is subjected to HPF at 750 °C, with very brittle behaviour in bending for 760 °C annealing + 750 °C HPF combination.

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